

DYNAMICS OF INTELLIGENCE OF LOW-SPEECH IN ADOLESCENTS

Mirzarakhimova Gulnora Ikromovna

Chirchik state pedagogical university

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Abstract. *Almost all psychologists define adolescence as the most critical age, as a transition between childhood and adulthood. The study of the patterns inherent in this stage of a person's life makes it possible to trace the transformation of children's psychological characteristics proper, which occurs within adolescence, as well as to identify the features of the maturing child's exit beyond childhood and the transition to maturity.*

The article deals with the concept of intelligence as a mental talent or the ability and dynamics of the intelligence of weak-speech teenagers.

Keywords: *adolescence, childhood, adulthood, psychological characteristics, maturity, intellect, talent, ability.*

Mental intelligence and spiritual potential are the two wings of an enlightened person. Therefore, in order to study the intellectual development of a person, it is advisable to carry out practical work that cannot be postponed. The problem of intelligence is one of the most studied topics in both foreign and domestic psychology. Although there are different approaches to elucidating the essence of intelligence, the general goal is to elucidate the intellectual development of man.

Psychologists view the concept of intelligence as a mental talent or ability. In foreign psychology, the concept of intelligence was introduced to quantify abilities and to describe them. The great psychologists of their time R.B. Cattell, L. Termin, C. Spearman and others created at the beginning of the 20th century. intellectual tests of various characteristics to measure the level of a person's abilities. The main goal arising from this is to make career choices in various specialties or to determine the suitability and competence of the profession [2].

The famous American psychologist F. Freeman puts forward the idea that intelligence consists of six components and tries to show and explain them:

1. Ability for numerical operations.
2. Vocabulary.
3. Similarity between geometric figures.
4. Speed of speech.
5. Ability to think.
6. Memory [3].

The famous scientist Torrance explores various aspects of general intelligence using statistical methods, generalizes them and calls them primary mental abilities and identifies 7 different abilities:

1. Computing abilities.
2. Oral verbal conciseness (flexibility), quick reading of speech.
3. Registration of verbal information (perception) or understanding of words.
4. Spatial action or grasping ability.
5. Memory.

6. Ability to think (discussion).

7. Speed of perception [4].

Speech is a type of human activity, the use of thinking based on language means. Speech performs the function of communication and communication, expressing one's thoughts with emotions and influencing others. Developed speech is one of the important means of active human activity in society, and for a student, speech is a means of successful learning at school. A child should be taught to speak fluently from an early age. For the development of students' speech, teachers need to use methods and techniques that help them actively master the pronunciation, vocabulary, syntactic construction and coherent speech of their students.

The purpose of teaching the native language is to teach students to think and use the means of expressing the language purposefully, in compliance with the norms of this language. It is important from an early age to teach a child to speak fluently, use beautiful words in his speech and freely express his thoughts. In the primary grades, students acquire theoretical and practical knowledge in all lessons, develop oral speech skills through the correct construction of sentences, rules of interaction, expression of opinion, re-creation of stories, memorization of poems.

In a modern school, the live speech of the teacher is supported by technical means. They increase the expressiveness of speech, enhance the emotional impact. In this case, the speech of the teacher becomes, as it were, unifying: it is perceived together with cinema, music, photo development. The word "teacher" also reflects special descriptive and expressive qualities. Since oral speech requires direct understanding in the process of perception, it acquires its own lexical and grammatical character.

The dynamics of the intelligence of children with speech defects is as follows:

1. Ensuring adequacy and flexibility in changing conditions;
2. Formation of mutually beneficial programs and plans in tactical and strategic areas, solution of current issues;
3. Planning events in interpersonal relationships and forecasting their development;
4. Motivation;
5. Increasing social competitiveness;
6. Self-education, self-consciousness, self-learning [5].

The dynamics of the intellect determines the neuropsychic state for a certain time, the factors of the social environment and the success of social relations, makes it possible to maintain with emotional stress, stress disorders, emergency situations, as well as in cases of personal denial.

The mobilizing function of intellectual dynamics is very important, which helps in cases of crisis, prolonged stress, understanding of self-esteem. The dynamics of the intellect makes it possible to predict and prepare for events occurring in relations between people, increases resistance to psychological stress.

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